

Sex and Infidelity in Manju Kapur's *Immigrant*

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : September

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Jeyaraman, C. S. "Sex and Infidelity in Manju Kapur's *Immigrant*." *Shanlax Internals Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 15–20.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3461743>

Abstract

Manju Kapur presents vagrant in woman married life. The novel Immigrant illustrate woman ruined by marriage, sex, immigration and infidelity. In Nina's case, it is her husband's Ananda's, pre-ejaculation that makes Nina go after Anton. Woman is not satisfied in her marital life. The sex is an important aspect of life. The female protagonist, Nina, is bent upon in outmaneuvering the male counterpart. This paper represents the modern and revolutionary woman of new generation in quest for definite identity of her own.

Keywords: immigration, migration, infidelity, sexual consummation, unfulfilled sex.

Manju Kapur presents vagrant in woman married life. The novel *Immigrant* illustrate woman ruined by marriage, sex, immigration and infidelity. In Nina's case, it is her husband's Ananda's, pre-ejaculation that makes Nina go after Anton. Woman is not satisfied in her marital life. She falls away from the expected roles and seize to be satisfied woman. She cross the boundaries and are tormented in her life struggle. The novel differs from all, as it has two locales one India and another Canada, and shuttles between these two. Its central character, Nina, is not only like Pipeelika of *Woman*, a Miranda House graduate but a teacher at that college and her Canadian destination, Halifax in Nova Scotia, is a location where Kapur has lived and studied.

The novel/story begins with the unmarried state of the thirty-year-old Nina, living with her widowed mother in a cramped Delhi apartment. Under the maternal pressure, she accepts a semi-arranged marriage with Ananda, an NRI dentist in Halifax, abandons her teaching career and moves to Canada. To her, the double process of adaptation to her husband and Canada is along one with pain and struggle. Nina joins a feminist group and spreads Simone de Beauvoir and Germaine Greer. Meanwhile, Ananda suffers from medical problems related to sex and seeks an alternative therapy in California. The therapy succeeds but the outcome is not to strengthen the marriage but to undermine it.

The story of the main character Nina's first night is one of disappointment as it reveals his dysfunction shattering her idea of a long and prolonged experience of sexual consummation. Though hurt with unfulfilled sex, she tries to suppress it with a positive

thought of togetherness in the true-spirit of marriage. Night after night, the experience continued to be the same with no fulfilment, leading to added frustration and loneliness. Though she has tried to fill her days with other activities such as going to the library and drowning whatever book that came her way, that cannot replace her physical and emotional fulfilment in marriage. When she suggests having sex frequently, Ananda takes it as her way of accusing him of his sexual dysfunction. Kapur writes: "For years and years Nina had masturbated, hoping the day would come when a loving partner would circumvent the furtive dissatisfied feeling this left her with [...] Guilt ridden, she would promise herself, this is the last time, but her restlessness made this impossible." (181)

When Nina attempted to be close to him he brushed her aside expressing his tiredness. This prompted her to close herself in the toilet to engage in her own self satisfaction. Nina seeks her own psychological satisfaction leading to more and more frustration. "In the beginning she had construed their problems to lie to their unfamiliarity to each other, even her body told her this in an itching which subsequently disappeared. His needs were obviously different and she didn't want to impose, hesitant about putting him off. If only she were in India, with more difficulties in her daily life...with more obligations." (181-82) She tried her best to educate herself to improve her sexual relationship with Ananda and to save their marriage. She read with fascination "quizzes about performance, seduction, techniques, adventure, libido, fantasy, daring, communication skills, verbal and physical etc." (182) All her readings led to need for mutuality as desires, fantasies and feelings to be shared. She openly shared her thoughts on improving their sexual relationship as he is unable to sustain himself due to premature ejaculation. She is frustrated as she points to the problem as the cause of her not conceiving.

Certainly Ananda decided to go on his own way as his problem made him hate Nina. His negative reaction to her suggestion to consult a therapist, disrupted their mutual trust and communication. After a few weeks, she sounded very positive when he spoke of a dental conference at San Diego. She was excited to go with him, but was put off when he decided to go alone. When he was gone Nina spent her days in more solitude. It was a secret trip he made to solve his sexual problem. "All his adult life he had been alone with this problem; it was the background to everything. For years he had felt abnormal, with a hidden disfigurement." (190) He was determined to undergo two weeks of therapy at Dr. Hanes's clinic to get his problem settled. But he kept the plan a secret. In the course of the sessions, he was given a surrogate named Marty in the absence of Nina to assist him with the experiments. She taught him to take focus on his sensations. The treatment consisted of daily two hourly sessions with Marty, mostly in bed with her to get him sustain his excitement, followed by counselling sessions. It was odd for him to play that sort of sex with a surrogate, but he had no other choice to make improvement in his premature ejaculation. Marty, being a professional sex therapist was keen on performing her tasks with precision, to get the best results for Ananda. She kept reminding him to focus on what goes on in his head in the course of the session. She taught him breathing exercises to reduce tension. He was surprised that one week into the therapy had not led him to having sex with Marty and he was learning things he could use in his relationship with Nina. Only his fear was how to tell Nina where he learnt all the new techniques. Marty reassured him if his wife really loved him, she would be glad he learnt the techniques from her.

Unfortunately, Nina was offered a part time job at the library; she found it an escape from her frustration. Kapur reveals Nina's thoughts very vividly: "I come almost every day; this is my home away from home. I used to teach literature in India, now I am getting to know Canadian authors... and I would love to unite my knowledge of books with more practical experience." (205) she was excited, but was not sure how Ananda would take the news. While unpacking his suitcase, she found several books on sex. She began to ponder on his secret way of going for sex therapy with the excuse of the conference. She wondered what kind of a therapy he had with a surrogate. She

was no fool and concluded that he had sex daily with someone else in the garb of a surrogate. Her thoughts flickered on why he resisted couple therapy at St. Louis instead preferred it with a surrogate in California. She should have known about it and the decision should have been hers. She could be glad that he has better staying power and the matter could end there without further questions. When he returned home that day he was beaming with joy as though he had missed her the whole day. Throwing off his coat he embraced her. She was eager to know about his sessions with the sex therapist. He was quick to retort and say that it was only a professional relationship. But she equated sex therapy to prostitution and made him feel very frustrated. The heated argument left them apart that night. The following day Nina tried to employ the technique he had taught her and told him. "Above all I want us to have a solid relationship, with us sharing everything. You are all I have in this country, you are the reason I am here." (211)

The need of hour, Ananda sought sexual fulfilment with his office clerk Mandy. He drove to her apartment at Clayton Park on a Saturday, where no one knew him. Finding the adulterous relationship growing stronger day by day, he decided never to give it up. The immediate impact was shown in his indifference to Nina. Though his visits to Mandy were exciting, she billed him for every minute he spent with her. His experiences with Mandy and Nina were totally different. "Mandy encouraged him to be wild, free, uninhibited, and playful. With Nina he was his mother's son, his sister's brother, the good husband, playing out a role he had been trained for since childhood. Nine years in Canada had not dimmed the need to be this person." (242) He was a split personality in his seeking fulfilment in his sexual explorations. Nina busied herself with her admission to the Library School. She was no more the solitary housewife of earlier times, depending for everything on her husband. "She was following the path her husband had trodden when he came here all those years ago, getting a degree that would affect the makeover of her Canadian identity. Two years was a small price to pay for such a metamorphosis, said Ananda." (247)

Nina met Anton in the school, a young Russian, married to a girl from West Indies. Finding Nina very warm and intelligent, he began to be close to her. Since both of them being married, he spoke in terms of platonic relationships between them like others in Canada. When a field trip was arranged for Nina to go to Ottawa, Ananda was very glad so that he could continue his clandestine affair with Mandy. When Mandy suspected that his wife would perhaps find a partner during the field trip, he was sure his wife would never do that. That was almost the breaking point in the relationship between Mandy and Ananda as she presumed herself to be the foremost in his life. He even told Mandy that he would die without her as she was considered his saviour. Though apparently all his desires were fulfilled after marriage, everything seemed to drill away. The only place where he felt fully himself was at his work, peering into people's mouth, which gave him recognition and "he thought of the empty spaces marriage had filled, the comfort of routine, and the daily companionship. It was marriage too, that had given him Mandy; in his mind his wife and his mistress was inextricably linked." (254) While in a restaurant on the last day of the trip, Nina sat next to Anton having a cigarette and had a couple of beers. Being impressed by his intelligent comments and jokes, she ignored his occasional touches and strokes. During the course of the conversation, he shared his perception of love and intimacy. "I'm married too. But it's stupid to confine yourself to one person for your whole life. What about adventure, what about experiencing differences? Nobody owns anybody, you know." (261) They held each other as they moved towards their hotel. She went with him to his room. In her loneliness, he overpowered her, and she found herself offering him everything. She begged him to stop, but finally collapsed into each other. She had her own justifications: "That she liked. She had lived. Who can feel guilty about living? Judging from the evidence, and the sexual therapy centres, every citizen in North America regarded good sex as their inalienable right, it was her right too." (263) She had a new perception of herself,

a sense of her own self, autonomous and independent from others. She did not feel guilty about her sexual adventures: "Her first lover had taken her virginity and her hopes, her second lover had been her husband, her third had made her international." (264) Their relationship being like an illusion, Anton kept away from Nina for a few days. But that made her suffer as they mutually desired each other. That was the beginning of her doing away with all taboos and traditions. She felt her beliefs were false.

During vacation, Anton would be going to New York, and she would miss him as she would be going to Delhi. When she returned after two months, Ananda was full of conversation. She felt pity for him and mused: "he must have missed talking when I wasn't here, poor man... Everybody needs someone, and fate has joined us together." (296) She felt guilty when he showed great pleasure in having her return home. She decided to devote herself to him, but felt it impossible to cross the barrier between them. Lightly, she asked if he had any affairs in her absence. The probing question put him off guard. They tried to enjoy each other's company. But Nina was determined with her obsession to have a child. In her mid thirties she felt insecure about a future with no children. In Canada she needed a broader base to rest on. She needed something more than Ananda in the home front after her profession was taken care of. Unlike in India, in Canada "it was all man-woman relationship-love-fulfilment." (299) The passionate expression of love from him left her dissatisfied as he refused to address the issue of having children.

Nina found joy in her library programme and was glad to undertake a field trip to New York. She took it an opportunity to continue with her relationship with Anton. Both Ananda and Nina were glad as they could both go their own ways. In course of a dinner out in a restaurant, Anton told her that their relationship had to remain purely on friendship basis. While returning together to her room in the International Student House, he asked her for a romantic evening with her. When she understood his sinister design she resisted his advances.

Back in Library School, Anton made efforts to apologise, but she ignored him. She couldn't go on like that for long and thought of bringing the matter to the women's group. But that would invite police investigation and case. Hence, she came to her own female conclusions: "Been foolish enough to be unaware of the links between former desires and present danger?" (316) When sex with her husband became difficult, one day she thought of giving a cooked up account of her trip. She said she was attacked by a man while on the street at night to snatch her chain. When Ananda questioned her why she had not reported it to him and the authorities, she began to weep. Nina's inner state of mind is contrasted with the setting of winter with its snow and icy wind as she wished to "escape into the purity of the landscape and be separated from her thoughts forever." (318) As the weather became warmer and green shoots propped up, she had green and fresh hopeful thoughts of a job of her own. As she entertained her prospective hope of happiness, news arrived of her mother's sudden death. Ananda arranged her to reach New Delhi the following day, enabling her to take her mother's ashes to be immersed in the Ganges at Rishikesh. With her mother gone, there was no one to call her own. She had no one's expectations to be met any more as her marriage bond meant nothing. "Her life was now completely her own responsibility, she could blame no one, turn to no one. She felt adult and bereft at the same time." (326)

Nina returned to Halifax, Ananda expressed his usual feelings of missing her all the while. The following morning, while making bed she noticed a wavy blond hair next to her pillow. Many things became clear to her as she sat with it on her bed: "The hair explained much the distance, the silence, the ticket for two months in India, his strange indifference interspersed with tenderness, the shifty look that skittered about her. She didn't blame him. His body spoke when his tongue could not." (327-28) She took the hair and taped it to the accounts notebook. She understood that marriage was based on more than one person's lies. Any exposure would only cause ruin and grief.

After mother's death, Ananda was her only anchor in the world in her loneliness. But all her hopes got shattered with the golden hair as it proved Ananda's adventures with white women. She had no other option but to go to the Library School. Anton made it a point to express his great regret for what happened, when she expressed her disgust for him, he pleaded forgiveness and absolution from her. She decided never to forgive him so that the crime would continue to wound him. It was a small victory for her. She wanted to encounter Ananda with evidences of his infidelity. But that would mean her own infidelity. They had to examine the core issue why they had betrayed each other. Ananda continued to sympathise with her mother's loss and comforted that things would change with a job. But she continued to be moody and stubborn behaving like a deprived immigrant. He tried his best to change her ways, but Nina continued to be his opposite even when he philosophised saying, "Life was what you make of it. You could look at a glass and call it half full or half empty. You could look out of the window and see the sky or stare at the mud." (330) Nina understood his comparisons and the argument and counter argument continue to taunt them. She accused him of being a drifter having no purpose in life, and seeing nothing beyond the material. He countered her saying Canada offered him everything in life, unlike her living in an unreal world. Her mind was made up: "She could not be happy living on the surface where he floated. For her that was not living at all." (331) But she was helpless in a foreign land without the security of her husband.

Finally, Ananda was a man under stress, considering himself unlike other immigrant Indians he knew. They all had a notion of home and family which they recreated in Canada. For him marriage was the only opportunity left for him to rebuild himself. But after marriage everything changed "his mind, his heart, his penis ... It was not her fault. It was the situation." (332) Nina had to enjoy every breath of air despite her stress as "her own regeneration was not inevitable as the revolving earth and the tilt of its axis." (332). She applied for jobs everywhere, except in Halifax as she needed a change to think over her life. She made it clear to Ananda that she wanted to be away from him to be independent. "She was travelling away from Halifax, deliberately pulling at the bonds that held her. She too was heading towards fresh territories, a different set of circumstances, a floating resident of the western world. When one was reinventing oneself, anywhere could be home. Pull up your shallow roots and move. Find a new place, new friends, and a new family. It had been possible once, it would be possible again." (333-34)

In this novel, the main story of a middle-class is globalised migrant in Canada, who's spatial and sequential identities are in a status of unvarying fluctuation as their lives become part of a challenge between different cultural perspectives. Kapur shows the dilemma of a middle-class migrant who are observed with a yearning of professional utopias and prosperous living and lifestyle and who willingly dispose themselves of from their homeland to assert a new identity. As the title indicates, Nina and Ananda's experiences are shaped by at least two major institutional and cultural apparatuses; India and Canada. The narrative concentrates more on Nina than on Ananda. It opens with Nina who lives with her widowed mother in a shabby flat at Jangpura in Delhi. She feels frustrated with the impoverished life she is leading. Nina's frustration arises more from her realization that the prospect of marriage and having a home of her own is going bleaker as she is on the verge of her thirtieth birthday. Besides, the bitter memory of her abortive affair with Rahul, a professor ten years older than her, who betrayed her even though she had had sexual consummation with him, haunts her and wounds her.

The sex is an important aspect of life. The female protagonist, Nina, is bent upon in outmaneuvering the male counterpart. Nina has had sex with the boy friend Rahul. After marriage, she finds her husband sexually dysfunctional. Kapur visualizes: "The bridal night. Now that the moment was close, Nina felt shy. Ananda closed the door and grabbed her. His hands leapt all over, under her

blouse, her petticoats; they forced her on the bed to enable an even speedier exploration of her body. Startled, she tried to slow him down, but in five minutes he had come, five minutes and he had not even entered her. The rest was done with his hands, but that was stuff she could have done on her own. Ananda disappeared into the bathroom. Nina had imagined a very different consummation. As she lay in bed she tried to transform reality into a scenario that would not confuse or upset her. Togetherness was the important thing. To be critical of how it was achieved was again the spirit of marriage. Involuntarily comparisons arose. Rahul, with his obsessive talk of sex, endlessly curious about what she felt in what position, this technique versus that. So much so that at time she felt objectified. At his desire to penetrate from behind she had been outraged, what did he think she was? His little virgin, he replied, who needed to be educated so they could feel as much pleasure as possible. That was what love was all about.” (89-90) After finding her husband sexually incompetent, she thinks of her independent career. However, Nina and Ananda both want to join the bandwagon of liberal sex. Nina gets a white parter Anton and Ananda gets a white female body of Mandy. Both desire each other.

Thus the novel, Nina represents the modern and revolutionary woman of new generation in quest for definite identity of her own. She shows an inclination towards assimilation and acceptance in the alien land. Nina's embodied identity is in a flux. It is inclined towards the land of living. There is no nostalgia of the past and rootlessness at the place of migration, a clinging to the old identity and a resistance to making a transition. The end of the novel finds Nina moving away from Ananda, uncertain of what the future will bring but nevertheless confident in her decision to leave. It is due to both Ananda's and Nina's infidelity.

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